

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND IMMUNE CELL STATUS IN COMORBID POOR-QUALITY TUMORS AND PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS

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Abstract

The coexistence of poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis significantly complicates diagnosis and treatment due to alterations in the morphological appearance and immune cell status. This study explores the morphological changes in tissues and the immune cell status in comorbid patients with poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis. A retrospective analysis of clinical and histopathological data from 130 patients revealed distinct morphological patterns and alterations in immune cell populations, including a decreased CD4+/CD8+ ratio and reduced NK cell activity. Understanding these changes can improve diagnostic accuracy and guide treatment strategies. This paper aims to enhance early detection and management of these comorbid conditions.

Keywords

- Poor-quality tumor
- Pulmonary tuberculosis
- Comorbidity
- Pathological process
- Immune cells
- Morphological changes

Relevance

Poor-quality tumors (PQT) and pulmonary tuberculosis (PT) are major global health challenges, each contributing to significant morbidity and mortality. Their coexistence presents significant clinical challenges due to their combined effects on pathological processes and the immune system. Immunosuppression caused by PQT predisposes patients to PT, complicating the clinical course and increasing diagnostic challenges due to overlapping symptoms.

Cancer remains a leading cause of death globally, with an estimated 10 million deaths in 2020. Pulmonary tuberculosis continues to be a significant

health issue, with 1.5 million deaths reported annually. The comorbid occurrence of PQT and PT complicates diagnosis due to the morphological similarity of cancerous and tuberculous lesions and alterations in immune cell populations. Comprehensive pathological and immunological studies are essential to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective treatment.

This research provides valuable insights into the morphological appearance of pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid conditions, helping healthcare professionals devise effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the morphological changes in pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid patients with poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods

This study retrospectively analyzed clinical and histopathological data from 130 patients diagnosed with PQT and PT between 2022 and 2024. Of these patients, 75 had lung cancer, 35 had gastrointestinal cancers, and 20 had breast cancer in conjunction with pulmonary tuberculosis.

A structured survey documented patients' age, gender, medical history, and initial symptoms. General patient information, clinical symptoms, disease duration, and comorbidity characteristics were studied.

Tissue samples from tumors and tuberculosis lesions were subjected to histological analysis to determine the morphological changes in pathological processes.

Cytological examination of biopsy samples helped identify immune cell populations and their status in comorbid conditions.

Immunohistochemical staining was performed to analyze immune cell markers and assess the state of immune cells, including T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, macrophages, and NK cells.

Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software. Parameters considered included:

- Average age and disease duration
- Type and extent of disease spread
- Immune cell marker expression levels

Conclusion

Comorbid Disease Morphology:

The comorbid occurrence of poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis presents unique morphological challenges due to overlapping pathological processes.

Comorbid conditions alter immune cell populations, with decreased CD4+/CD8+ ratios and reduced NK cell activity, indicating immune suppression.

Accurate diagnosis requires comprehensive histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis, and treatment strategies should address immune suppression and comorbidity.

- Routine screening for comorbid conditions should be implemented.

- Immunohistochemical analysis should be integrated into the diagnostic process to assess immune cell status.

- Clinicians should adopt individualized approaches in managing PQT and PT.

Understanding the morphological changes in pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis can guide clinicians in devising effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

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